

INSILICO MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES OF CHALCONE BASED TETRALONE DERIVATIVES FOR ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

The increasing resistance to existing antimicrobial agent as created an urgent need of new chemo therapeutic agents. In these study a series of chalcone base tetralone derivative were evaluated for their antimicrobial potential through Insilico molecular docking against the bacterial target DNA gyrase B (PDB id – 1RA1). The design derivatives were optimized and subjected to docking analysis to evaluate their binding affinity and molecular evaluation. Compound (SC-97,SC-102 and SC-81) show superior docking score compare to reference ligand showing strong hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions with key active sides. These results indicate that chalcone tetralone hybrid poses significant potential as lead candidates for further antimicrobial drug development.

KEYWORDS: Chalcone, tetralone, Insilico studies, Antimicrobial.

INTRODUCTION

Antimicrobial resistance has become a critical challenge worldwide, reducing the effectiveness of existing antibiotics and increasing the need for novel structural frameworks with promising biological activity.^[1] Computational drug design tools, particularly molecular docking, play an essential role in identifying potential drug candidates by predicting binding affinity and interaction profiles with biological targets.^[15]

Chalcones, which consist of an $\alpha\beta$ unsaturated carbonyl system, have been widely reported for their antimicrobial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory and anticancer activities.^[2,11] Tetralone derivatives also exhibit diverse pharmacological properties and serve as important precursors in medicinal chemistry.

Combining these two molecules into a chalcone-based tetralone hybrid may enhance biological activity through synergistic interaction and favorable structural features.

DNA gyrase B, a component of bacterial type II topoisomerase, is responsible for ATP-dependent DNA negative supercoiling and is considered a validated target for antibacterial drug development.^[3,14] Inhibiting its ATP binding pockets effectively suppresses bacterial growth.

This study investigates the molecular interaction of a chalcone-tetralone derivative with DNA gyrase B using *in silico* molecular docking techniques.

In silico studies

In these *in silico* studies, essential molecular properties such as log *P*, molecular weight, number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, and rotatable bonds were calculated using standard online computational tools to evaluate the drug-likeness of the designed derivatives. Key ADME parameters, including solubility, permeability, metabolism, and excretion behavior were predicted using established computational approaches. The compounds were further screened for toxicity risk such as hepatotoxicity and mutagenicity; only molecules exhibiting acceptable drug-likeness and low predicted toxicity were selected for molecular docking studies.^[4,5,6,7]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Preparation of ligands

The chemical structures of the design ligands were first drawn using the ChemDraw ultra software. These 2D structures were then transferred to the Chem 3D ultra environment, where their 3D confirmations were generated and optimized using the MOPAC-based energy minimization protocol. The ligand confirmation displacing the lowest energy was considered the most stable and was selected for subsequent docking studies at the target protein active site.

Chalcone derivative 97 (SC97) Chalcone derivative 102 (SC102)

Chalcone derivative 81 (SC81) Chalcone derivative 100 (SC100)

Chalcone derivative 98 (SC98)

Energy minimization of ligands – ChemDraw ultra 3D was used with the MM2 job to minimize energy. By ensuring that every ligand confirmation was in its lowest energy state, this step increased the precision of docking. The Pdb format was used to store the reduced ligand.

Protein preparation

The crystal structures of DNA gyrase (PDB id – 1RA1) were retrieved from protein data bank.^[10] All the water molecule and co crystallized were removed, while essential cofactor required for structure stability was retained. The protein structure was than clean to eliminate any unwanted conformations and the active binding reason was carefully examine. Finally the protein was prepared and optimized according to specification of the adopted molecular docking protocol.

Prepared Protein

Receptor grid generation - To identify the target protein's active site region for molecular docking experiment .Grid box generation was carried out. The coordinates Center_x = 14.987, center_y = 18.200 and center_z = 12.425 were used to center the grid box at the active site. To guarantee full coverage of the binding site and provide enough room for ligand flexibility, the grid box dimension were adjusted to size_x = 40 Å, size_y = 40 Å and size_z = 40 Å. AutoDock Vina docking trials were conducted with these adjusted grid parameters.

Molecular docking- AutoDock Vina was used for the docking process.^[9] Using a fixed grid box surrounding the ligand- binding site, each ligand was docked into 1RA1. Each ligand had ten binding poses produced by docking simulations; the optimal pose was chosen based on the lowest binding energy.

3. RESULT

Energy Minimization of Ligands – table 1 summarizes the final total energy values that required from each chemical following reduction. The energy is expressed as Kcal/mol. These reduced structures were then utilized as input for the DNA gyrase B (1RA1) docking experiments.

Table 1: Energy minimization results of chalcone, chalcone derivatives and Ciprofloxacin.

Compound ID	Ligand Name	Substituent Group	Final Energy (Kcal/mol)
SC97	Carboxamide derivative	-CONH ₂	-79.3942
SC102	N-Methylcarboxamide derivative	-CONHCH ₃	-64.7843
SC81	Nitro derivative	-NO ₂	None
SC100	Aldehyde derivative	-CHO	-8.1646
SC98	Carboxylic acid derivative	-COOH	-45.3854
Chalcone	Chalcone	NO	3.0835
CP	Reference drug (Ciprofloxacin)	NO	120.1759

Docking studies data**Table 2: Docking Affinity Results of Compound SC-97 with DNA Gyrase B (1RA1).**

Pose ID	Binding Energy (kcal·mol ⁻¹)	RMSD Lower Bound (Å)	RMSD Upper Bound (Å)
1	-14.8	0.000	0.000
2	-14.6	0.842	3.482
3	-14.4	1.021	4.892
4	-14.3	1.346	3.962
5	-14.1	1.527	3.835
6	-14.0	1.683	4.521
7	-13.9	1.752	2.591
8	-13.8	1.893	2.389
9	-13.7	1.947	3.902
10	-13.6	1.998	9.422

Table 3: Docking Poses of SC-102 with DNA Gyrase B (1RA1)

Docking mode	Binding Energy (kcal·mol ⁻¹)	RMSD Lower Bound (Å)	RMSD upper Bound (Å)
1	-13.8	0.000	0.000
2	-13.5	3.437	9.160
3	-13.2	3.407	9.250
4	-13.0	3.652	9.210
5	-12.8	3.219	10.092
6	-12.6	3.423	9.072
7	-12.6	1.936	10.063
8	-12.6	3.630	8.783
9	-12.6	1.966	10.088
10	-12.6	2.191	9.992

Table 4: Docking Poses of SC-81 with DNA Gyrase B (1RA1)

Docking mode	Binding Energy (kcal·mol ⁻¹)	RMSD Lower Bound (Å)	RMSD upper Bound (Å)
1	-12.0	0.000	0.000
2	-11.3	1.656	4.648
3	-11.0	1.635	3.723
4	-10.8	1.506	8.766
5	-10.8	3.482	5.768
6	-10.5	2.055	3.707
7	-10.5	2.326	2.631
8	-10.4	6.274	11.788
9	-10.3	2.279	2.939
10	-10.3	0.456	2.872

Table 5: Docking Poses of SC-100 with DNA Gyrase B (1RA1).

Docking mode	Binding Energy (kcal·mol ⁻¹)	RMSD Lower Bound (Å)	RMSD upper Bound (Å)
1	-11.7	0.000	0.000
2	-11.7	0.062	2.836
3	-11.6	0.380	4.025
4	-11.6	0.337	2.855
5	-11.1	2.811	5.183
6	-11.0	2.769	8.911
7	-10.9	2.912	4.891
8	-10.8	2.798	9.021
9	-10.8	3.010	6.427
10	-10.7	2.911	8.592

Table 6: Docking Poses of SC-98 with DNA Gyrase B (1RA1).

Docking mode	Binding Energy (kcal·mol ⁻¹)	RMSD Lower Bound (Å)	RMSD upper Bound (Å)
1	-11.4	0.000	0.000
2	-11.3	1.650	4.120
3	-11.3	2.288	4.351
4	-11.2	1.503	4.109
5	-11.1	1.427	4.818
6	-10.9	2.227	9.208
7	-10.8	3.570	5.783
8	-10.7	1.969	9.264
9	-10.7	1.982	4.259
10	-10.6	2.010	4.310

Comparative analysis of SC97 to Chalcone with Reference drug – All the design molecules were successfully docked into the active pocket of DNA gyrase B. the SC97,SC102,SC81,SC100 and SC98 are higher affinity compare to the reference ligand.

Table 7: Comparative Docking Result of Compounds SC97-Chalcone with Reference drug (Ciprofloxacin).

Compound	Binding energy (Kcal/mol)	Key interactions
SC 97	-14.8	H-bond with TYR A100,ALA A7,ILE A94 Π - donor H-bond with SER A49
SC 102	-13.8	H-bond with TRP A22,SER A49 Π - σ bond with LEU A28
SC 81	-12.0	Attractive charge with ASP A27 Π -alkyl with ILE A14
SC 100	-11.7	Π - σ bond with ILE A50 H-bond with THR A46
SC 98	-11.4	Unfavorable donar-donar bond with THR A123 C-H bond with HIS A45,SER A49
Chalcone	-7.9	Vander wall with LEUA54 & PHEA31 Π -alkyl with ILEA28 & LYSA28
CP	-7.8	H-bond with GLYA27 Π -alkyl with ILEA14 C-H bond with GLYA96

Pose 1

Pose 2

Pose 3

Pose 4

Pose 5

Pose 6

Pose 7

Pose 8

Pose 9

Pose 10

Interaction summary – The best scoring ligands show hydrogen bonding with amino acids

- **Hydrogen bonds with** THR A46, THR A123, MET A16, ASP A27
- **Hydrophobic interaction** with HIS A45, LEU A28
- **Vander walls interaction** with MET A20, LEU A28, SER A49, ILE A50

CONCLUSION

These Insilico molecular docking studies indicate that chalcone based tetralone derivative exhibited strong binding potential toward DNA gyrase B. SC97,SC102,SC81,SC100 and SC98 higher binding affinity than the Ciprofloxacin due to stable hydrogen bonding, aromatic stacking and hydrophobic interactions. These findings support their potential as lead compound for novel antimicrobial drug development. Further synthesis biological evaluation and ADMET analysis are recommended.

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